

Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y buffer layer deposited by chemical bath deposition for low and wide bandgap Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ solar cells

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Abstract

Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ (CIGSe) solar cells with a tunable bandgap stand out as a promising technology for tandem applications. Addressing the environmental concerns associated with Cd-based buffers, this study investigates the suitability of zinc tin oxide (ZTO), deposited via chemical bath deposition (CBD), as a Cd-free alternative for both low-bandgap CIGSe and wide-bandgap (Ag,Cu)(In,Ga)Se₂ (ACIGSe) solar cells. Best ZTO-buffered devices exhibit competitive power conversion efficiencies (PCE) of 14% and 7% for low-bandgap and wide-bandgap absorbers, respectively. The optimal tin concentration for ZTO buffer layers vary, with 10%

[Sn]/([Sn]+[Zn]) ratio (TTZ) identified as optimal for wide-gap ACIGSe and 20% TTZ for low-gap CIGSe. A performance decline beyond optimal tin concentrations could be linked to losses in open-circuit voltage. In summary, ZTO-based devices showcase promising photovoltaic performance, emphasizing ZTO's potential as a practical and non-toxic alternative, deposited by CBD, to traditional CdS for diverse CIGSe solar cell applications.

1. Introduction

The urgency of addressing the ongoing environmental crisis has powered the exploration of renewable energy sources, with solar power emerging as a significant contributor, constituting 15% of global renewable energy.^[1] Among photovoltaic technologies, Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ (CIGSe) stands out for its potential in flexible, semitransparent, and tandem applications. This is attributed to its tunable bandgap (1.0–1.7 eV) and high absorption coefficient ($>10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)^[2–4], making it a promising candidate for the production of clean and sustainable energy, with a laboratory power conversion efficiency (PCE) record of 23.6% (including Ag alloying).^[5]

Tandem solar cells, involving stacking multiple absorbers with varying bandgaps, offer a pathway to enhance efficiency.^[6] CIGSe, with its adjustable bandgap, is well-suited for integration as either the top or bottom cell in tandem devices. However, challenges arise, particularly in the performance of wide-bandgap CIGSe with a high [Ga]/([Ga]+[In]) ratio (GGI), which exhibits lower efficiency than anticipated, mostly related to losses in open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}). As a consequence, CIGSe presents an optimum GGI in the region of 0.25–0.30,^[7,8] which has been assigned to several reasons including presence of Ga-rich compounds, as well as increase of bulk and interface recombination.^[9,10] An increasing GGI also modifies the band alignment between absorber and the traditional CdS buffer layer.^[11] Addressing this challenge, partly replacing the copper lattice sites with silver has shown improvement in the V_{oc} , related to better conduction band offset between high-Ga (Ag,Cu)(In,Ga)Se₂ (ACIGSe) and the buffer layer, with a maximum PCE of 15.1% for an absorber bandgap of 1.45 eV and a 16.3% when a RbF post-deposition treatment is applied ($E_g = 1.44 \text{ eV}$).^[12,13]

Traditional CdS, with its narrow bandgap ($E_g = 2.4 \text{ eV}$), partly prevents high-energy photons to be absorbed by CIGSe.^[14] Furthermore, for wide-bandgap applications it can increase the interface recombination due to its low electron affinity ($\chi = 4.25 \text{ eV}$), related to a negative conductive band offset (CBO).^[4,15] In this context, less-toxic wide-bandgap buffers such as Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y (ZTO), In₂S₃, and Zn(O, S), among others have garnered attention.^[16–19] ZTO, fabricated by atomic layer deposition (ALD), has outperformed CdS due to gains in short-circuit current (J_{sc}) related to absorption of high-energy photons,^[16,20] and gains in V_{oc} associated to better band alignment, especially for wide-bandgap CIGSe.^[15]

Recently, we developed a solution-based method for depositing thick ZTO buffer layers by ammonia-based chemical bath deposition (CBD). This method allows for the tunability of the

ZTO bandgap (3.2–3.6 eV) by adjusting the $[\text{Sn}]/([\text{Sn}]+[\text{Zn}])$ ratio (TTZ), providing a non-toxic alternative for wide-bandgap applications. This study reported an average PCE of $9 \pm 2\%$ for an absorber of 1.16 eV and a ZTO buffer with nominal TTZ of 20% ($\sim 10 - 12\%$ in the film).^[18] Moreover, CBD is recognized for its low-temperature ($<100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) process, ensuring conformal growth in a reliable, cost-effective, and batch-scalable manner.^[21]

Motivated by the promising outcomes of ZTO produced by ALD in both low and wide bandgap CIGSe, we fabricated high-efficient CIGSe solar cells with ZTO buffer layers using CBD. In this study, we investigate the current density-voltage (JV) characteristics of solar cell devices employing ZTO and CdS buffer layers, applied to both low-bandgap CIGSe (without silver alloying) and wide-bandgap ACIGSe, providing insights on the potential of ZTO as an effective buffer layer in CIGSe solar cells.

2. Results and discussion

We fabricated low-bandgap CIGSe solar cells without a highly resistive layer depositing the conductive ZnO:Al (AZO) layers by sputtering directly on top of the buffer layers. Cross sectional scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images (**Figure 1**) show that for different TTZ in the bath deposition the buffer layer thickness varies. This variation indicates that the effect of Sn in the bath goes beyond modifying the ZTO bandgap or the ZTO/CIGS interface, as previously reported.^[18] For similar deposition time, the concentration of Sn in the bath also influences the thickness of the thin film. Nonetheless, no clear trend was observed and further investigation regarding the growth mechanism in the ZTO CBD process is required.

Figure 1. SEM cross-section images of low-bandgap devices with ZTO buffers of a) 10, b) 20, c) 25, and d) 30% TTZ. The left half of each image is artificially colored to guide the reader with colors corresponding to each layer: CIGSe (blue), ZTO (green) and AZO (gray).

CIGSe solar cells with the ZTO buffer prepared from the 20% TTZ bath exhibit the best performance (**Figure 2**), yielding a mean PCE of $(12 \pm 3) \%$ [$J_{sc, EQE} = (38 \pm 2) \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$; $FF = (60 \pm 9) \%$; $V_{oc} = (520 \pm 34) \text{ mV}$], which is slightly lower than the CdS-based devices with a mean PCE of $(13.7 \pm 0.5) \%$ [$J_{sc, EQE} = (37 \pm 1) \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$; $FF = (66.7 \pm 0.6) \%$; $V_{oc} = (561 \pm 6) \text{ mV}$]. It is worth noting that the ZTO layer obtained from this bath corresponds to the thickest buffer, with an average thickness of $(0.21 \pm 0.08) \mu\text{m}$. However, beyond 20% TTZ, a significant decline in performance was observed, caused by substantial losses in V_{oc} and FF.

Figure 2. Solar cell parameters for CdS-based and ZTO-based devices with low bandgap CIGSe with different compositions of ZTO buffer layers: a) power conversion efficiency, b) short-circuit current density, c) fill factor, and d) open-circuit voltage.

To further investigate the ZTO structure and the low-bandgap CIGS/ZTO interface, **Figure 3** shows the high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) images and elemental maps for ZTO based solar cells prepared from baths with TTZ of 10, 20, and 30% (Low magnification HAADF images can be seen in **Figure S1**). The elemental maps of selenium are displayed to indicate the position of the ZTO/CIGSe interface. The apparent presence of Sn in the CIGSe layer is attributed to an overlap of the characteristic

X-ray lines of In and Sn. In agreement with our previous report,^[18] the 10% TTZ ZTO based devices exhibit some Sn-rich regions at the interface. Nonetheless, 20% TTZ ZTO solar cells display a more homogeneous distribution of Sn across the buffer layer, with an increase in concentration close to the interface with the absorber. At 30% TTZ, a thin Sn-rich layer is observed at the ZTO/CIGSe interface, suggesting formation of mainly a SnO_x interlayer, which could lead to a negative band offset with respect to CIGSe.^[22] The latter is better observed on the elemental profiles across the CIGSe/ZTO/AZO interfaces (**Figure S2**) and the elemental maps for oxygen (**Figure S3**), which exhibit a higher concentration of Sn at the interface with CIGSe for all devices. It is worth mentioning that this result displays the complexity of the CBD process where the substrate plays an important role in the deposition of ZTO thin layers; for example, this thin SnO_x interlayer was not observed in our previous study.^[18]

These Sn-rich regions are likely responsible for the open-circuit voltage drop (see Fig. 2), caused by changes in the band alignment. The possible presence of SnO_x at the CIGS/ZTO interface would lead to a lower conduction band minimum (CBM) than ZnO, which could lead to a negative band offset with respect to CIGSe, as shown in the simulations in the supplementary information.^[15,22] It is also worth noting that the thinner buffer layers obtained from the 10% and 30% TTZ baths exhibited different performance in terms of V_{oc} and FF, suggesting that thickness alone cannot account for the observed performance variations. SEM imaging revealed average thicknesses of (0.12 ± 0.04) and (0.13 ± 0.08) μm for 10 and 30% TTZ samples, respectively (see Fig. 1).

Figure 3. HAADF-STEM images of the ZTO with low-bandgap CIGSe solar cells: a) ZTO buffer layer with 10% TTZ, b–e) corresponding elemental maps from the area of the HAADF image for Sn+Se, Se (blue), Zn (red), and Sn (yellow) acquired by EDS. f) ZTO buffer layer with 20% TTZ and g–j) corresponding elemental maps from the area of the HAADF image for Sn+Se, Se, Zn, and Sn; k) ZTO buffer layer with 30% TTZ and l–o) corresponding elemental maps.

Between 10 and 20% TTZ devices, the champion cells significantly differ due to an average difference in open-circuit voltage of 70 mV. Based on our previous report, the change from 10% to 20% TTZ in the bath corresponds to a change from 7 to 12% TTZ in the film (**Table S5**). Therefore, the Sn concentration in this range emerges as a critical parameter influencing the device's final performance.^[18,23]

Figure 4 shows the JV curves and EQE spectra for the low-bandgap CIGSe champion solar cells. All ZTO-based devices show improved carrier collection from high-energy photons due to the difference in bandgap between ZTO and CdS.^[18] Furthermore, the EQE spectra for higher TTZ, 25 and 30%, show an initial onset at lower wavelengths, presumably related to a slightly wider bandgap for these layers.^[18] The champion cells for 10, 25 and 30 % TTZ show a current loss in the near infrared region compared to CdS, presumably related to recombination at the ZTO/CIGS interface. In addition, the EQE spectra show that the bandgap of the absorbers is comparable for all samples with a value of 1.03 eV.

Figure 4. a) EQE spectra and b) JV curves under illumination for the best low-bandgap CIGSe solar cells with CdS and ZTO buffer layers.

In terms of the champion solar cells, the solar cells with 20% TTZ ZTO buffer exhibit a performance similar to that of the reference cells with a CdS buffer, with a gain in $J_{sc, EQE}$ of about 1 mA cm^{-2} and a loss in V_{oc} of 15 mV. This aligns with our latest reports, where a $\sim 350\text{ nm}$ ZTO buffer showed optimal performance.^[18,19] However, thick buffer layers may generate performance losses due to the high resistivity of ZTO thin films. Nonetheless, our efforts on the deposition of thinner buffers resulted in inhomogeneous coverage. In addition, considering reports on ALD-ZTO buffer layers with thicknesses as low as 20 nm,^[20] further investigation into the impact of the ZTO buffer thickness is essential for a complete understanding of its effects on Cd-free CIGSe solar cells.

Figure 5 shows SEM cross section images of the wide-bandgap ACIGSe/ZTO interfaces. For these devices the ZTO layers showed a similar morphology as AZO layers, which makes their distinction more difficult. Furthermore, ZTO layers seem to be thin but the imaging did not allow a clear measurement of the thickness. These changes in the ZTO buffer showcase the importance of the absorber (surface) in the CBD process, where different absorbers could promote or inhibit the growth of specific ZTO orientations.^[24] However, the details of the ZTO growth are still unknown and further research is needed. One hypothesis relates to the process of nucleation, in which some crystal facets favor the growth while others inhibit it. Another possibility can be associated to a differential adsorption of metallic cations during the initial growth phase. Studies on Zn(S,O) buffer layers report also the effect of solution mixing on the

final device performance related mainly with the deposition of particles/clusters,^[25] so further research on the CBD process is necessary.

Figure 5. SEM cross-section images of ACIGSe wide-bandgap devices with ZTO buffers of a) 10%, b) 13%, c) 17%, d) 20%, and e) 30% TTZ. The left half of each image is artificially colored to guide the reader with colors corresponding to each layer: CIGSe (blue), ZTO (green) and AZO (gray).

Regarding the solar cell parameters for wide-bandgap ACIGSe (**Figure 6**), we show several CdS references to account for differences in the absorber composition due to the geometry of the deposition system and the absence of substrate rotation creating compositional gradients in the absorber for the same deposition (**Table 1**). Regarding the differences within the CdS reference devices, an increase in performance variation was observed, which can be attributed to slight variations in the absorber layer. Nonetheless, the average PCE, FF, and V_{oc} of the CdS reference devices do not differ significantly at a 95% confidence level, whereas the J_{sc} shows a statistically significant difference between the references. Therefore, we conclude that it is valid to directly compare the overall solar cell performance across the different ZTO buffer layers, although the short-circuit current should not be directly compared. When comparing the ZTO-based devices with their respective CdS references, a gain in J_{sc} is observed for baths with a TTZ below 20%.

The 10% TTZ ZTO sample displays the best performance with a mean PCE of $(6 \pm 1) \%$ [$J_{sc, EQE} = (14 \pm 2) \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$; $FF = (64 \pm 11) \%$; $V_{oc} = (622 \pm 26) \text{ mV}$]. In contrast, the best CdS reference shows a mean PCE of $(7 \pm 2) \%$ [$J_{sc, EQE} = (12.9 \pm 0.6) \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$; $FF = (63 \pm 14) \%$; $V_{oc} = (785 \pm 98) \text{ mV}$]. Also for the wide-bandgap absorber the fill factor is not significantly different compared to the CdS reference, which could indicate a less resistive front contact due to a thinner ZTO buffer layer. Likewise, we observed a similar trend with lower performance when increasing the TTZ, mostly related to losses in V_{oc} , similar to the case of low-bandgap CIGSe. Overall, the performance level of all wide-gap ACIGS cells is lower than previously

reported, since the absorber composition was unintentionally very group-I poor ($[I]/[III] \sim 0.7$), which might lead to the formation of detrimental ordered vacancy compounds at the surface and corresponding electron collection losses.^[26]

Figure 6. Solar cell parameters for CdS-based and ZTO-based devices with wide-bandgap ACIGSe with different compositions of ZTO buffer layers: a) power conversion efficiency, b) short-circuit current density, c) fill factor, and d) open-circuit voltage.

It is known that silver alloying in wide-bandgap ACIGSe promotes better band alignment at the ACIGSe/buffer interface. Silver lowers the CBM, in contrast to increasing GGI, which raises the CBM, thereby allowing fine tuning of the absorber bands to match the buffer bands.^[15] However, for the studied samples, absorber composition modifications were not significant. In this study, the ZTO buffer corresponding to the lowest bandgap (~ 3.44 eV)^[18] and highest electron affinity (~ 4.44 eV)^[23] outperformed the other ZTO buffers and displayed a PCE only ≈ 1 %-point lower than the CdS reference. Assuming that the studied absorber behaves as the ones simulated by Keller et. al.^[15], the studied absorber has a CBM close to 4.26 eV, which is very similar to the electron affinity of CdS ($\chi = 4.25$ eV), thus the ACIGSe/CdS CBO should be close to zero.

Device simulations performed in SCAPS-1D show that an uniform ZTO buffer layer shows a CBO of -100meV, which corresponds to a cliff (**Figure S4**). This cliff could be related to the loss in V_{oc} , which has an average difference of 0.2 V compared to the CdS reference. Further simulations varying the thickness and bandgap of a uniform ZTO buffer layer show a stronger dependence of the solar cell parameters on the thickness of the buffer layer (**Figure S5**), with thinner buffers resulting in gains in efficiency and current, while thicker ZTO are related to better open-circuit voltage. The buffer layers change with the nominal TTZ in the deposition bath, which translates to a higher bandgap with lower thickness for high TTZ contents, thus these buffers rest within the trends observed in the simulated devices. Therefore, further characterization of the ZTO growth by CBD is required to optimize its structure, TTZ, and thickness, and thereby boost the final device performance, especially in terms of V_{oc} .

To further characterize the ACIGSe/ZTO interface, **Figure 7** shows the HAADF-STEM imaging of the wide-bandgap devices (low magnification HAADF images can be seen in **Figure S6**). Unlike SEM imaging, the STEM images allow a clear distinction between the buffer and AZO layers (**Figure S7**). However, determining the exact thickness from these data is challenging because of the inhomogeneity commonly observed in ZTO prepared by CBD. The buffer thicknesses are below 100 nm, with thinner buffers as the TTZ increases. Contrary to the low-bandgap samples, the 10% TTZ device shows a homogenous distribution of Sn across the ZTO layer, while the 20% TTZ sample exhibits localized Sn-rich regions, as previously reported.^[18]

Figure 7. HAADF-STEM images of the ZTO with wide-bandgap CIGSe solar cells. For each sample, the HAADF image together with the corresponding elemental maps for Sn+Se, Se (blue), Zn (red), and Sn (yellow) acquired by EDS are shown. The images correspond to devices with a ZTO buffer layer with TTZ of a-e) 10 %, f-j) 20 %, and k-o) 30 %.

Simulated devices with a double buffer layer composed of a thin SnO₂ layer and a ZTO layer (details of the simulation in the supporting information, **Table S5**) show a harmful effect of the thin SnO₂ layer on the device performance on both low (**Figure S8**) and wide (**Figure S9**) bandgap CIGSe, mainly impacting the V_{oc} . Furthermore, the simulated devices with thin SnO₂ layer show poorer performance with the increase of the ZTO bandgap, due to pronounced cliffs (-130 and -290 meV for low and wide bandgap devices, respectively) in the conduction band alignment. As observed above, the thickness of the ZTO layer decreases for higher TTZ. According to literature, thinner ZTO buffer layers prepared by ALD have been reported to yield higher V_{oc} values compared to their thicker counterparts^[20], yet this trend does not hold for the CBD-grown ZTO layers or the simulated devices. Our data indicate that this difference is since higher concentrations in Sn not only result in thinner layers but also in accumulation of Sn-rich regions at the interface with the absorber. Although thinner devices work better, according to literature and simulations, the accumulation of Sn has a stronger impact on the performance of the device, affecting both its V_{oc} and J_{sc} .

Furthermore, for the 30%TTZ sample the elemental maps shows that Sn mainly accumulates at the interface with the absorber, similar to the case of low-bandgap CIGSe, but there is not a clear continuity within the Sn-rich regions. The latter can be also observed in the elemental profiles across the ACIGSe/ZTO/AZO interfaces (**Figure S10**), where a peak in Sn content is only observed for the 30% TTZ sample. Likewise, these Sn-rich regions, which mainly are composed of SnO_x, are detrimental for the final device performance.

Figure 8 shows the JV curves and EQE spectra for the champion cells with the wide-bandgap ACIGSe absorber. The CdS-based reference device outperforms all ZTO-based devices mainly due to a V_{oc} of 0.8 V; the 10% TTZ ZTO based device achieves 0.64 V. We attribute this loss in open-circuit voltage to both the thickness and the CBO cliff at the ACIGSe/ZTO interface, based on the simulations performed. This contrasts with the reported observation of a “spike” configuration and a gain in V_{oc} for thin ALD-ZTO.^[15] Furthermore, the EQE spectrum for the 10% TTZ ZTO-based device shows higher photon absorption for all wavelengths compared to other studied buffers. EQE spectra also show no parasitic absorption in the blue region due to

the substitution of CdS, together with a slightly oscillatory behavior, previously observed and attributed to high reflectance.^[15,18]

Figure 8. a) JV curves under illumination and b) EQE spectra for the best wide-bandgap ACIGSe solar cells with CdS and ZTO buffer layers.

Assuming a reproducible process, the films grown in the 10% TTZ bath are expected to have a Sn content close to 7% (**Table S6**), different from the optimal value of ~20% found for ALD-ZTO buffer layers for wide-bandgap ACIGSe.^[15,16] Nevertheless, by considering the STEM imaging, a higher TTZ content gives rise to the formation of Sn-rich regions that are detrimental to the final device performance. This indicates that an ideal ZTO buffer layer for wide-bandgap CIGSe must have a higher Sn content without the presence of Sn-rich regions or inhomogeneities at the interface with the absorber.

For both absorbers studied, ZTO buffers prepared with a 30% TTZ present low performance due to losses in both FF and V_{oc} , mainly related with the presence of a thin Sn-rich layer at the CIGSe/ZTO interface that creates a cliff arrangement, resulting in losses in FF, in agreement with the simulations shown in the supplementary information. Furthermore, based on the EDS the best performance corresponds to the most homogenous buffer layer in terms of Sn content, but it is interesting to notice that the substrate plays a role in the distribution of Sn within the ZTO layer, being 10% TTZ for ACIGSe and 20% TTZ for CIGSe, even though the buffer deposition baths were similar for both substrates.

3. Conclusion

In this study, ZTO buffer layers were successfully deposited by CBD on both low-bandgap CIGSe and wide-bandgap ACIGSe absorbers, achieving competitive PCE of 14% and 7%,

respectively. The optimization process revealed distinct optimal nominal tin concentrations in the bath deposition for the two absorbers, with 10% TTZ ZTO identified as optimal for the wide-bandgap samples, and 20% TTZ ZTO for the low-bandgap material. A pronounced decline in performance was observed for both materials when higher Sn content buffer layers were used, mainly due to losses in open-circuit voltage. These open circuit voltage losses presumably stem from poor band alignment, providing a plausible explanation for the results obtained in the low-bandgap CIGSe sample. Further characterization of the CIGSe/ZTO interface showed that the best performance devices for both low and high bandgap absorbers present a more homogenous buffer layer and in both cases the presence of Sn-rich regions (presumably SnO_x), locally creating a unfavorable negative conduction band offset, which is detrimental to the final device performance. In addition, the results showcase the importance of the substrate in the CBD of ZTO, as similar bath conditions gave result to different thin films in terms of morphology and Sn composition.

Overall, ZTO-based devices demonstrated promising photovoltaic performance with PCE values of $(12 \pm 3)\%$ for low-bandgap CIGSe and $(6 \pm 1)\%$ for wide-bandgap ACIGSe. For both types of absorbers, ZTO-based devices show a performance that is not significantly different compared to CdS-based references, even though CdS champion reference cells surpass ZTO champion cells. Further optimization in the control of the Sn distribution within the buffer layer is required. These results emphasize the viability of ZTO, deposited by CBD, as a practical and non-toxic alternative to CdS for both wide- and low-bandgap CIGSe solar cells.

4. Experimental Methods

The absorber layers of the devices were deposited using a three-stage co-evaporation process, with a maximum temperature of 550 °C; further details can be found elsewhere.^[27] Chemical bath deposition was used for both the CdS and ZTO buffer layers. After absorber deposition a protective CdS layer was deposited on top of the absorber by CBD. The deposition bath was prepared by the consecutive addition of NH₄OH (4.4 % v/v), cadmium acetate (17 m M), and thiourea (0.35 M). The depositions were carried out at 60 °C for 8.5 minutes. Prior to the ZTO deposition, an HCl-etching was done for 90s with HCl ~9% to remove the protective CdS layer. The ZTO deposition bath was prepared by the consecutive addition of aliquots of ZnSO₄, NH₄OH, ethanolamine, and SnCl₂ (prepared in HCl 1.7M) stock solutions to obtain a final concentration of 75 mM of cations ($[Zn^{2+}] + [Sn^{2+}]$), 0.2 M NH₄OH, and 1.6 M ethanolamine. The depositions were carried out at 92 °C for 30 min with a variation of TTZ in the range of

10%–30%.^{18]}. Then, the ZnO:Al front contact ($\sim 0.21 \mu\text{m}$) was deposited directly on top of the buffer by RF sputtering. Finally the solar cells were mechanically scribed with an area of 0.05 cm^2 and measured directly on the front contact. **Table 1** shows the composition of the absorbers used in this study, based on X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis

Table 1. Sample names of the investigated solar cells and corresponding integral atomic composition ratios as well as bandgap, estimated from EQE measurements.

Sample	Composition			E _g [eV]
	I/III	GGI	AAC	
Low-bandgap CIGSe	0.91	0.24	0.0	1.03
Wide-bandgap ACIGSe	0.67-0.74	0.68-0.69	0.24-0.26	1.46

Device characterization

Completed solar cells were characterized by external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements and by JV analysis at $T = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under illumination by an ELH lamp in home-built setups. Illumination intensity was adjusted to the short-circuit current density as extracted from the EQE spectra ($J_{\text{SC, EQE}}$). The bandgap of the absorbers was estimated as the x-intercept of a linear regression following a linear fit, where $(\ln(1-\text{EQE}) \times E)^2 \propto E - E_g$.

Cross-section micrographs of the finished devices were obtained by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in an FEI Quanta 50 FEG SEM. Furthermore, these devices were also analyzed by scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Firstly, cross-sectional samples were prepared using a FEI Helios NanoLab 450S focused ion beam (FIB) to have electron-transparent lamellae (thickness $< 100 \text{ nm}$) for subsequent STEM/EDS analysis. The FIB operates with a gallium (Ga) liquid metal ion source, which is the reason why we deliberately abstain from quantifying the Ga content in the analyzed samples. Secondly, high-angle annular dark field (HAADF) STEM imaging was performed with a probe-corrected FEI Titan G2 80-200 keV ChemiSTEM (wide-bandgap ACIGSe devices), and double-corrected FEI Titan G3 Cubed Themis 60-300 keV (low-bandgap CIGSe devices), both operated at 200 keV.

While using the double-corrected Titan Themis, the images, captured at a resolution of 2048×2048 pixels, were acquired using a 21 mrad convergence angle and a pixel dwell time of $8 \mu\text{s}$. For elemental mapping, EDS analysis was performed using a Super-X EDS detector. Iterative maps of 2048×2048 pixels were collected with a pixel dwell time of $5 \mu\text{s}$ at 200 keV, under beam current ranging from 150 to 250 pA, with a total acquisition time of 15 minutes. The

STEM-EDS data was acquired and processed using Velox software from Thermo Fisher Scientific. Regarding the probe-corrected ChemiSTEM, the images of 2048×2048 pixels were recorded using a convergence angle of 21 mrad with pixel dwell time set to 8 μ s. EDS-mapping was performed with the same instrument using a Super-X EDS detector. Iterative maps of 1024×1024 pixels were recorded with a dwell time per pixel of 13 μ s at 200 keV, and collection times of at least 15 min. The software Esprit from Bruker was used for acquiring and processing the STEM-EDS data.

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Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Considering the importance of Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) solar cells for tandem applications, we study Cd-free low and wide-bandgap CIGSe solar cells, based on the chemical bath deposition of Zn-Sn-O as an alternative buffer layer. The fabricated solar cells show a similar performance as CdS based reference, which proves the viability of this non-toxic buffer layer.

Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y buffer layer deposited by chemical bath deposition for low and wide bandgap Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ solar cells

ToC figure: 55 mm broad × 50 mm high

Supporting Information

Zn_{1-x}Sn_xO_y buffer layer deposited by chemical bath deposition for low and wide bandgap Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ solar cells

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Table S1. Parameters of the champion cell for low bandgap CIGSe samples.

Parameter	CdS	10% TTZ ZTO	20% TTZ ZTO	25% TTZ ZTO	30% TTZ ZTO
J _{sc} [mA cm ⁻²]	38	39	39	37	39
V _{oc} [mV]	563	474	548	378	396
FF [%]	67.9	60	67	45	52
PCE [%]	14.3	11	14	6.3	8

Table S2. Average parameters for low bandgap CIGSe samples.

Parameter	CdS	10% TTZ ZTO	20% TTZ ZTO	25% TTZ ZTO	30% TTZ ZTO
J _{sc} [mA cm ⁻²]	37 ± 1	35 ± 4	38 ± 2	34 ± 2	36 ± 2
V _{oc} [mV]	561 ± 6	441 ± 89	520 ± 34	388 ± 7	361 ± 20
FF [%]	66.7 ± 0.6	51 ± 12	60 ± 9	40 ± 4	45 ± 4
PCE [%]	13.7 ± 0.5	9 ± 3	12 ± 3	5.3 ± 0.8	6 ± 1

Table S3. Parameters of the champion cell for wide bandgap ACIGSe samples.

Parameter	CdS ^a	10% TTZ ZTO	13% TTZ ZTO	17% TTZ ZTO	20% TTZ ZTO	30% TTZ ZTO
J _{sc} [mA cm ⁻²]	13.8	16	13	13	13	12
V _{oc} [mV]	833	642	600	491	578	331
FF [%]	73	71	62	53	56	52
PCE [%]	8	7	5	3	4	2

a) Data from the best CdS reference.

Table S4. Average parameters for wide bandgap ACIGSe samples.

Parameter	CdS ^a	10% TTZ ZTO	13% TTZ ZTO	17% TTZ ZTO	20% TTZ ZTO	30% TTZ ZTO
J _{sc} [mA cm ⁻²]	12.9 ± 0.6	14 ± 2	13 ± 1	12.1 ± 0.8	9 ± 2	10 ± 2
V _{oc} [mV]	785 ± 98	622 ± 26	481 ± 113	376 ± 56	537 ± 42	308 ± 39
FF [%]	63 ± 14	64 ± 11	54 ± 11	48 ± 4	50 ± 3	47 ± 6
PCE [%]	7 ± 2	6 ± 1	4 ± 1	2.2 ± 0.6	2.4 ± 0.7	1.5 ± 0.4

a) Data from the best CdS reference.

Device simulations were performed using SCAPS-1D to investigate the influence of buffer-layer thickness and optoelectronic properties.² The simulated device structure consisted of a CIGSe/Buffer/AZO stack, using either CdS or ZTO as the buffer layer. The front and back contacts were defined with flat-band conditions and a surface recombination velocity of 1×10^7 cm s⁻¹ for both electrons and holes.

A CdS reference device was first simulated, and several (A)CIGSe parameters were adjusted to match the experimental data, taking the measured band gap into account (**Figure S11**). The adjusted parameters included the conduction band density of states (N_C), valence band density of states (N_V), defect capture cross sections for electrons and holes, the shallow acceptor density, and the total defect concentration. In addition, the electron affinities of the absorbers were calculated using an equation derived from computational results and the measured AAC and GGI values for both absorbers.³ Table S5 summarizes the parameters used in the simulations. A constant charge-carrier velocity of 1×10^7 cm s⁻¹ was applied in all layers.

Table S5. Parameters used in SCAPS-1D simulations of the fabricated devices.

Material	CIGSe	ACIGSe	CdS	ZTO ^{4,5,6}	AZO	SnO ₂ ⁷
Thickness (μm)	2.0	2.0	0.05	0.2*	0.304	0.01
Bandgap (eV)	1.03	1.46	2.4	3.4*	3.464	3.6
Electron affinity (eV)	4.42	4.26	4.25	4.4*	4.6	4.55

Dielectric permittivity	13.6	13.6	10	9	10	9
N_c (cm ⁻³)	2.15×10^{17}	1.00×10^{18}	2×10^{18}	2.2×10^{18}	4×10^{18}	2.2×10^{18}
N_v (cm ⁻³)	2.15×10^{16}	1.00×10^{16}	1.5×10^{19}	1.8×10^{19}	9×10^{18}	1.8×10^{19}
Electron mobility (cm ² .Vs ⁻¹)	100	100	50	160	1.1	100
Hole mobility (cm ² .Vs ⁻¹)	25	25	20	40	1.1	25
Donor Density (cm ⁻³)	-	-	1×10^{15}	1×10^{14}	1.1×10^{21}	5×10^{14}
Acceptor Density (cm ⁻³)	1.00×10^{16}	1.00×10^{15}	-	-	-	-
Defect type	Neutral	Neutral	-	Single Donor	-	Single Donor
Capture cross section electrons (cm ²)	4.64×10^{-14}	1.87×10^{-16}	-	1×10^{-11}	-	1×10^{-11}
Capture cross section holes (cm ²)	2.15×10^{-15}	1.87×10^{-16}	-	1×10^{-11}	-	1×10^{-11}
Energetic distribution	Single	Single	-	Single	-	Single
Reference	Above EV	Above EV	-	Below EC	-	Below EC
Energy level with respect to Reference (eV)	0.6	0.6	-	0.8	-	0.8
N_t total (cm ⁻³)	1.00×10^{17}	1.00×10^{19}	-	1×10^{17}	-	1×10^{17}

* Parameters changed during the ZTO simulations

To simulate the ZTO-based devices, two idealized buffer configurations were considered: (i) a uniform ZTO layer and (ii) a bilayer consisting of a thin SnO₂ layer followed by a uniform ZTO layer. These structures were chosen based on the STEM observations presented in the main manuscript.

For the uniform ZTO layer, the first set of simulations was intentionally simplified to isolate the effect of the electron affinity. In this case, the bandgap and remaining material properties were kept constant, while only the electron affinity was varied. **Figures S12** and **S13** show the resulting JV curves for the (A)CIGSe devices. For the low-bandgap CIGSe, the simulations reveal that buffers with low electron affinity significantly degrade the device performance, with optimal behaviour occurring near $\chi \approx 4.42$ eV. In contrast, the simulated wide-bandgap ACIGSe

devices exhibit smaller variations with electron affinity, with a maximum performance around $\chi \approx 4.26$ eV.

To achieve more realistic predictions, a second set of simulations was performed by estimating the electron affinity under the common assumption that Sn incorporation primarily affects the conduction band of the ZTO layer.⁴ Under this approximation, the electron affinity was set as $\chi = 7.8 - E_g$, while the remaining optoelectronic parameters were obtained from literature values for ZTO or fitted to match experimental trends. In all cases, the conduction-band offset (CBO) is derived directly from the simulated band diagrams. Figures S5 and S14 present the simulated solar cell parameters for the uniform ZTO layer using this approach.

Finally, Figures S8 and S9 show the simulated band diagrams and JV characteristics for the bilayer configuration (CIGSe/SnO₂/ZTO), which was included to reflect the inhomogeneity observed in the STEM images.

Figure S1. HAADF-STEM images of low-bandgap CIGSe devices with ZTO buffer layers: (a-c) Low magnification cross-section images of devices with a with a ZTO buffer layer with TTZ of a) 10 %, b) 20 %, and c) 30 %; (d-f) high-magnification images showcasing the ZTO/CIGSe interface with with TTZ of d) 10 %, e) 20 %, and f) 30 %

Figure S2. HAADF-STEM images of low-bandgap CIGSe devices with ZTO buffer layers, together with the respective line profiles of Zn (red), Sn (green), O (gray) and Se (violet) across the CIGSe/ZTO/ZnO:Al interface as indicated by the vertical arrow for the buffer layers of (a, b) 10%, (c, d) 20% and (e, f) 30% TTZ. For clarity, the apparent Se signal in the profile lines is considered an artefact caused by spectral interference with the Pt lines.

Figure S3. HAADF-STEM images of the ZTO with low-bandgap CIGSe solar cells: a) ZTO buffer layer with 10% TTZ, b, c) corresponding elemental maps from the area of the HAADF image for O (green) and Sn (yellow) acquired by EDS. d) ZTO buffer layer with 20% TTZ and e, f) corresponding elemental maps from the area of the HAADF image for O and Sn; g) ZTO buffer layer with 30% TTZ and h, i) corresponding elemental maps.

Figure S4. Simulated band diagrams for ZTO-based devices with different bandgaps and a buffer thickness of 200 nm: a) low-bandgap CIGSe and b) wide-bandgap ACIGSe. In both cases the CBO was calculated based on the simulated band diagrams. The lowest CBO (black line) corresponds to a ZTO with bandgap of 3.4 eV ($\chi=4.4$ eV), while the highest CBO (red line) corresponds to a ZTO with bandgap of 3.6 eV ($\chi=4.2$ eV).

Figure S5. Simulated solar cell parameters for ZTO-based devices with wide-bandgap ACIGSe with different ZTO bandgap and thickness: a) power conversion efficiency, b) short-circuit current density, c) fill factor, and d) open-circuit voltage.

Figure S6. HAADF-STEM images of wide-bandgap ACIGSe devices with ZTO buffer layers: (a-c) Low magnification cross-section images of devices with a with a ZTO buffer layer with TTZ of a) 10 %, b) 20 %, and c) 30 %; (d-f) high-magnification images showcasing the ZTO/CIGSe interface with with TTZ of d) 10 %, e) 20 %, and f) 30 %

Figure S7. HAADF-STEM images of the ZTO with wide-bandgap CIGSe solar cells: a) ZTO buffer layer with 10% TTZ, b, c) corresponding elemental maps from the area of the HAADF image for O (green) and Sn (yellow) acquired by EDS. d) ZTO buffer layer with 20% TTZ and e, f) corresponding elemental maps from the area of the HAADF image for O and Sn; g) ZTO buffer layer with 30% TTZ and h, i) corresponding elemental maps.

Figure S8. a) Simulated band diagrams for ZTO-based low bandgap devices with different bandgaps with the buffer being simulated with a thin SnO_2 interlayer (10 nm) between CIGSe and ZTO and b) corresponding simulated JV curves. The lowest CBO (blue line) corresponds to a ZTO with bandgap of 3.4 eV ($\chi=4.4$ eV), while the highest CBO (green line) was calculated with a ZTO with bandgap of 3.6 eV ($\chi=4.2$ eV).

Figure S9. a) Simulated band diagrams for ZTO-based wide bandgap devices with different bandgaps with the buffer being simulated with a thin SnO_2 interlayer (10 nm) between ACIGSe and ZTO and b) corresponding simulated JV curves. The lowest CBO (blue line) corresponds to a ZTO with bandgap of 3.4 eV ($\chi=4.4$ eV), while the highest CBO (green line) was calculated with a ZTO with bandgap of 3.6 eV ($\chi=4.2$ eV).

Figure S10. HAADF-STEM images of wide-bandgap CIGSe devices with ZTO buffer layers, together with the respective line profiles of Zn (red), Sn (green), O (gray) and Se (violet) across the CIGSe/ZTO/ZnO:Al interface as indicated by the vertical arrow for the buffer layers of (a, b) 10%, (c, d) 20% and (e, f) 30% TtZ.

Figure S11. Simulated and experimental JV curves for CdS reference devices: a) low-bandgap CIGSe and b) wide-bandgap ACIGSe.

Figure S12. Simulated JV curves and JV parameters for low bandgap CIGS devices with ZTO buffers and a constant ZTO bandgap of 3.4 eV, the variation corresponds only to changes in the ZTO electron affinity: a) JV curves, b) power conversion efficiency, c) short-circuit current density, d) fill factor, and e) open-circuit voltage.

Figure S13. Simulated JV curves and JV parameters for wide bandgap ACIGS devices with ZTO buffers and a constant ZTO bandgap of 3.4 eV, the variation corresponds only to changes in the ZTO electron affinity: a) JV curves, b) power conversion efficiency, c) short-circuit current density, d) fill factor, and e) open-circuit voltage.

Figure S14. Simulated solar cell parameters for ZTO-based devices with low-bandgap CIGSe with different ZTO bandgap and thickness: a) power conversion efficiency, b) short-circuit current density, c) fill factor, and d) open-circuit voltage.

Table S6. TTZ composition in the buffer layer for different TTZ in the bath measured by ICP on top of CIGSe substrates.¹

TTZ in solution [%]	TTZ in the film [%]
10	7 ± 4
20	12 ± 3
30	9 ± 3
40	28 ± 8

$$TTZ = \frac{[Sn]}{[Sn] + [Zn]}$$

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